

The Need for Healthy Menus of Airline Passengers

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ABSTRACT : This paper aimed to study the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers. The sample group consisted of Airline passengers (400 persons) in Thailand. They were obtained by convenience sampling and did not rely on possibility. A set of questionnaires was used for data collection and analyzed by using descriptive statistics. Also, there was an analysis of relationships of guidelines for The Need for Healthy Menus having an effect Airline passengers Thailand An analysis of correlation coefficient value and multi-stage multiple regression analysis were employed. Results of the study revealed that The Need for Healthy Menus on product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .01$) and marketing strategies on price (X_5) ($\beta = 0.314$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers.

KEYWORDS - need ;healthy; menus.

I. INTRODUCTION

From the World Food Market in 2015, there is an increase in the health of Thai people. Especially the elderly, most of them turn to taking care of their health And eating more healthy food, Thailand has The tendency to enter the aging society with the population aged 65 years and over more than 20 percent of the total population. Or clean food More Because of the benefits of healthy food Help promote health And reduce the risk of Pathogenesis, such as reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease, reducing the risk of cancer and Many benefits, etc. Can be eaten in normal people. Including the sick Because it may reduce the risk of disease That occur or prevent subsequent complications or improve health Have more benefits than those who don't Eat all kinds of healthy foods.[1]

And in the present way of working life In general, Thai people do not have time to complete normal food supply. Therefore causing anxiety and fear of being absent Nutrients and is also believed to have effects on health in terms of prevention and cure various ailments that Caused by the changing lifestyles of people in the urban society who are stressed at work. There is no time to rest Exercising and polluting pollution occurs all around until causing many Thai people to have a need for treatment Self health by "Buying health for money" Different types of food, especially products Supplements in the form of powders, tablets, capsules and liquids. [2] According to the 2015 World Food Market Report, consumers are increasingly turning to healthy food, with a focus on products made of natural blends. High-Protein Foods Complex carbohydrates And control weight Reducing the amount of sweetness and salinity used in cooking and serving foods rich in good fats. And that food has to contribute to the digestive system. According to the association Researching in the United States that in 2014, 60% of the Americans were predominantly Which is a group of consumers aged 15-30 years and consumers aged 55 years and over are mostly consumers with purchasing power, preferring to eat specialty foods or kale. Foods are foods that have a high production quantity of raw materials and perforators. And the food that is given Health benefits than conventional food As a result, the value of the food market that focuses on high quality raw materials has a value of 88, 300 million baht and is expected to grow further this year. [3]

Therefore, consumers need to maintain a balanced diet. And wish not to hurt and hurt, as well as to have a further effect on the wellbeing Consumers therefore began to link food consumption and health to each other. If consuming good food Will have a positive effect on physical and mental health Of that consumer [4]

Differences in perceived health are different. It is one thing that affects the decision to consume because of the different health awareness among consumers. Will affect the influence of making food choices Consuming foods that will cause good or bad color will directly affect your decision to buy healthy food. In addition, the awareness of the value of healthy food will influence behavioral changes. [5]

From the policy of aviation liberalization to promote tourism Of the Thai government and intra-group aviation liberalization agreements ASEAN countries It will take effect in full in 2015. Resulting in various airlines Increase the number of flights into Thailand Continually, the aviation business has to face the competitive environment that consistently intense as today's consumers are demanding Diverse and rapidly changing business groups Therefore, airlines need to modify the format of Operate with a focus on running a comprehensive business. And meet the needs of customers in every market segment [6]

As a result, more groups of the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers. It is interested in doing research on the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers.To be a guideline for the the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers. and to build confidence in foreign tourists. This could enable economic recovery in the service industry to return to normal and rapid growth.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives of this research article were to study of the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The framework of this quantitative research is based on related concepts and theories to study the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers. with details as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of this study

Research Methodology

Population and sample group

The population was the Airline passengers (400 persons) in Thailand. The sample group consisted of 400 respondents by non-probability sampling and accidental sampling. The number was obtained by calculating the formula without the population at a 95% confidence level, and the sample size was set as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = Size of the sample group

Z = Reliability level

P = Proportion of the population

E = Highest error value which will happen

The acceptance level was in accordance with the statistical significance level at 0.5

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$= 384.16$$

The sample size was 385 respondents. However, 400 questionnaires were gathered by using a probabilistic sampling method between June - October 2020.

Research Instrument

The research tool was a questionnaire where the samples were asked individually to provide information about the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers. The content consisted of 4 parts as follows.

Part 1 : General information of the respondents, namely gender, age.

Part 2 : Data related to guidelines for the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers

Part 3 : Data related to relationships of the guidelines.

Part 4 : Problems encountered and suggestions about the guidelines.

Data analyses

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires in the form of filling in information online to provide convenience and speed to comply with the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the concordance between the the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers and the set of results by analyzing the correlation coefficient and stepwise multiple regression.

IV. RESULTS

Table 1 Results the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers

Marketing	Model 1			Model 2		
	B	SE B	β	B	SE	β
x ₁ : product	0.419	0.052	0.456**	0.418	0.057	0.412**
x ₅ price				0.542	0.076	0.314*
R ²		0.345			0.313	
R ² Change					0.051	
F for change in R ²					4.445*	

Dependent Variable : the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers (Y) * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

According to Table 1, it was found that the Need for Healthy Menus on product (X₁) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .01$) and marketing strategies on price (X₅) ($\beta = 0.314$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers with a statistical significance level. This could be explained that variance of guidelines for the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers to elevate the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers for (R² = 0.345). The predicting equation of the guidelines as a holistic dimension (Y) in the form of standard score was $Z_y = 0.412Z_{x_1} + 0.314Z_{x_5}$

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results revealed that overall the Need for Healthy Menus on product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.412$, $\alpha < .01$) and marketing strategies on price (X_5) ($\beta = 0.314$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers with a statistical significance level. This could be explained that variance of guidelines for the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers to elevate the Need for Healthy Menus of Airline passengers for ($R^2 = 0.345$). The predicting equation of the guidelines as a holistic dimension (Y) in the form of standard score was $Z_y = 0.412Z_{x_1} + 0.314Z_{x_5}$ Consumer behavior means the actions of a person. It involves making a selection, buying (Purchase), using (Use) and getting rid of the rest of goods or services in order to meet their needs. individuals or groups in the procurement, selection, purchase, use and post-consumer handling of the product. Or services to meet the needs of consumers over a period of time [7] each human being will change according to the circumstances of the environment. And seeks the need to understand oneself Accept oneself in the good and the glitches are known their own weaknesses and abilities every human being has a need to satisfy his own needs. All and the needs of human beings are many different things. Which must be satisfied from require the lowest basics before they pass up to the respective higher requirements Consisting of (1) physical needs It is the lowest basic human need for survival (2) the need for safety or stability. When humans are able to meet their physical needs Humans will continue to increase their needs at a higher level. People can Meet the physical needs Humans will continue to increase their needs to a higher level (3).Need love And social needs This requirement will Occurs when the physical demands And the need for safety has already been met. (4) the need for lifting Sneaking or self-esteem It is a need to be respected and respected. Status from society and (5) the need for success in life. (Self-Actualization) is the highest demand Individual. [8] Healthy food is the food that provides energy. And various nutrients that are essential to the function of The body for the body to grow, have an immune system, help repair various functional systems of the body It is normal and leads to good health. And longevity Eating foods that fit the body in action. Everyday life must be eaten in 5 groups. Because each food contains nutrients Various types in different quantities Which each nutrient gives different benefits to the body, therefore Eating to be healthy Therefore, many foods should be eaten in the amount that is appropriate for Age and physical condition For the body to grow And developed appropriately, which has divided the food Principles of Thai people according to nutrients And characteristics of food into 5 groups and food can be classified Into 6 kinds [9]

VI. CONCLUSION

Beliefs about food are culturally passed down from one generation to the next. Dietary beliefs and behaviors were bred from childhood. And Meat baht is very important to both In family units and cultural groups Food plays a role in both childhood and adulthood in Associate a member group with a kinship group. The two functions of food consumption are the creation of identity. Of the individual through food consumption And make people included in the society Prep and join Well, eating food is considered a way to bring people to the same community. Therefore, food has a market. It is important to differentiate between cultures and to strengthen them within the group. In order to understand food as an commodity, it is imperative that it be understood. The role of the impact of commercial advertising in visualizing food. Many products are marketed to differentiate themselves from their competitors, so advertising and packaging are trying to find the right visualization for consumers. It is not necessary to Take into account the value of nutrients, flavors and ingredients very much. Especially in some products such as carbonated drinks, desserts, sauces, frozen or canned food. Characteristics and values Symbols are very important in establishing the meaning of food products such as snacks, sodas, and even healthy foods. Some values will be added, such as youthfulness, strength, sexual attraction. And more fun than taste in eating Food or drink there.

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